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Benchmarking of prediction tools to explore the plasmidome of *Salmonella enterica*

DOUARRE P.E.¹, BARBET P.², FELTEN A.¹, RADOMSKI N.³, CADEL-SIX S.¹, MISTOU M.Y.⁴

¹ Anses, 14 rue Pierre et Marie Curie, 94700, Maisons-Alfort, France

² INRAE, University of Paris-Saclay, Métagenopolis, Jouy-en-Josas, France

³ Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale, National Reference Centre (NRC) for Whole Genome Sequencing of microbial pathogens

⁴ INRAE, University of Paris-Saclay, Centre International de Ressource Microbienne, Unité MalAGE, Jouy-en-Josas, France

Plasmids are widespread in the species *Salmonella enterica*, one of the most important food borne pathogen causing zoonotic infection. They contribute to the virulence of specific serovar and the expansion of resistant clones in the food chain. Identifying plasmids is therefore critical to better understand the transmission of resistant and virulent plasmids in *S. enterica*. Several tools, based on various approaches (coverage analysis, k-mer-based classification, replicon detection...) are currently available to assess the plasmidome from draft assemblies. However, prediction with high sensitivity and specificity is difficult to achieve and recovering plasmid sequences from contigs is still challenging. Here, we have conducted a benchmarking of five recent plasmids prediction tools using different approach to target the plasmidome of *S. enterica*.

A reference dataset of 55 known *S. enterica* genomes including 50 genomes carrying from one to five plasmids (n=81) of various sizes was created. This dataset was tested against PlaScope, PlasFlow, HyAsP and MOB-recon and Platon with three different plasmid databases created for this study. The performance of the prediction tools were evaluated by calculating various scores based on the presence of true/false positive/negative contigs. The tool presenting the best performance was finally used to explore the plasmidome of a collection of 2863 *S. enterica* genome. All reconstructed plasmids were classified by replicon & MOB-typing and were screened for the presence of AMR determinants.

The overall performance of the reference-based tools vary with the database used and the presence of *S. enterica* plasmid sequences can severely affect the precision of MOB-recon and HyAsP. Filtering contigs smaller than 1000bp improved all metrics except the recall by decreasing the number of false positive. All the tools achieve high specificity and accuracy while the precision and the recall varied the most among the different tools. PlaScope outperformed all the other tools in precision and also attained highest F1 score along with HyAsP and Platon. PlaScope finally reconstructed 1894 plasmids from the *S. enterica* genome collection of which 225 carried antimicrobial resistant markers. Our findings revealed interesting resistant plasmid clusters that were either restricted to a specific serovar or distributed among unrelated *S. enterica* genomes.

1. Introduction

Plasmids are extra-chromosomal fragments that are ubiquitous in bacterial genomes (Shintani et al., 2015). They carry adaptive genes such as resistance and virulence genes that confer a selective advantage to bacteria (de Toro et al., 2014). They can transfer between different species and therefore play an important role in the dissemination of drug-resistant bacteria (Smillie et al., 2010; Carattoli, 2013).

Salmonella genus represents the most common foodborne pathogen responsible for zoonotic infections in a broad host range including humans, wild and domestic animals (Knodler and Elfenbein, 2019). Salmonella can be transmitted to humans through contaminated foods of animal origin and are important causes of gastroenteritis and bacteraemia. Thus, Salmonella infections represent a worldwide threat to public health, animals, and food industry (Eng et al., 2015; Jajere, 2019). Within the most pathogenic species, *Salmonella enterica* (*S. enterica*), over 2600 different serovars have been identified to date (Jajere, 2019). While most serovars can cause disease in humans, a small number of serovars display association with a particular animal species: for example, *S. enterica* serotype Dublin in bovine and *S. enterica* serotype Choleraesuis in swine (Chiu et al., 2004; Paudyal et al., 2019). It has also been shown in the last decades that the monophasic Salmonella Serovar 1,4,5,12:i:- is one of the most common serovar isolated from humans and foods worldwide (Aladueña et al., 1999; Yang et al., 2015). The global expansion of this particular serovar is strongly associated with the acquisition of antimicrobial determinants (Guerra et al., 2000; Garcia et al., 2013). The “Spanish” clone encodes a plasmid conferring resistance to seven antimicrobial drugs including ampicillin, chloramphenicol, gentamicin, streptomycin, sulfonamides, tetracyclines, and trimethoprim (Guerra et al., 2001; Garcia et al., 2011). Several studies also reported the presence of plasmids conferring resistance to extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) (Wiesner et al., 2009; Wasyl et al., 2015) and to diverse classes of antibiotics in different serovars (Harmer et al., 2015; Mutai et al., 2019). The virulence of *S. enterica* is also mediated through the expression of a virulent plasmid, which carry the *spv* operon, required for the virulent phenotype in mice (Guiney and Fierer, 2011). Related virulent plasmids have been identified in eight serovars including Paratyphi C, Enteritidis, Dublin, Gallinarum/Pullorum and Choleraesuis (Feng et al., 2012). Multi Drug Resistant (MDR) plasmids encoding *spv* or other virulence factors such as heavy metal resistance genes has also been reported in several studies (Wiesner et al., 2009; Billman-Jacobe et al., 2018; Mutai et al., 2019). The accurate identification of the plasmidome is therefore critical to track the evolution and the spread of these resistant bacteria.

The affordable cost of sequencing has led to an explosion in the amount of genomic data. As of this writing (28/10/2020), 272175 assembled genomes of Salmonella are present in the Enterobase database (Zhou et al., 2020). Differentiating plasmid- and chromosome-associated contig from genome assemblies is still challenging. To tackle this issue, several prediction tools using different approaches have been developed along with the creation of diverse plasmid databases (Galata et al., 2019; Jesus et al., 2019; Douarre et al., 2020). Among these *in silico* tools: PlasmidFinder searches for plasmid replicons markers in bacterial assemblies from a database mainly composed of Enterobacteriaceae replicons (Carattoli et al., 2014); MOB-recon uses a database of reference plasmids and collections of known replicons and relaxases (Robertson and Nash, 2018); PlaScope is also a targeted approach to recover plasmidic sequences at the species level (Royer et al., 2018). Recycler and plasmidSPAdes do not depend on reference sequences and predicts plasmids from the assembly graph based on read-depth and length features (Antipov et al., 2016; Rozov et al., 2017). cBar, PlasFlow and mlPlasmids use machine learning approach to classify k-mer frequencies (Zhou and Xu, 2010; Arredondo-Alonso et al., 2018; Krawczyk et al., 2018); Platon measures the protein-coding genes' replicon distributions to distinguish between plasmid- and chromosome-related contigs and further characterize contigs using different approach (Schwengers et al., 2020); HyAsP (Hybrid Assembler for Plasmids) identifies and assembles plasmid from an

assembly graph using information from known plasmid genes, read depth and GC content (Muller and Chauve, 2019). It combines a reference-based method and a greedy assembly algorithm.

Here, we have selected five *in silico* prediction tools using different methods (HyAsP, MOB-recon, PlasFlow, PlaScope and Platon) that we tested against 55 known genomes of *S. enterica* including 81 known plasmids. Three plasmid databases were created and several runs of predictions using different filters and parameters were performed. The aim of the study is to assess and compare the performance of the predictions tools for the identification of *S. enterica* plasmids. The tool presenting the best performance both in terms of specificity and sensitivity was integrated into a pipeline and tested against a collection of 2863 genomes for the complete characterization of the plasmidome. All the reconstructed plasmids were classified by replicon and MOBtyping and resistance genotype was determined using BLASTn search and ResFinder. The distribution of plasmid types and resistant plasmids among different serovars was examined to predict potential transmission.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Reference dataset

A reference dataset of 55 known complete genomes of *S. enterica* including 50 genomes carrying from one to five plasmids (n=81) of various sizes (from 1814 to 298919 bp) and five genomes without plasmids was created. Artificial reads (paired end, 150 bp, 100X coverage) were created for the five “control” genomes from the chromosome sequences (NC_011294.1, AE006468.2, CP006876.1, CP001144.1 and CP029486.1) using ART to guarantee the absence of plasmid reads (Huang et al., 2012). For the other 50 genomes, corresponding reads and assemblies were downloaded from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the NCBI Nucleotide archive, respectively. The 55 *S. enterica* genomes belong to four different *subspecies* (87.5% from the subspecies *enterica*) and 35 different serovars. All the information regarding the strains, the reads, the assemblies as well as the number and size of plasmid are summarized in the Supplementary Table S1 and S2.

In order to control that the short reads from all the individual samples cover both chromosomal and plasmid sequences, the reads were aligned using BWA with standard parameter against the corresponding chromosomes and plasmids (complete sequences) and the depth/breadth of coverage were calculated using SAM-tools (Li et al., 2009).

The short reads were then assembled with SPAdes v3.13.0 with standard parameter and “careful” option and the assembly quality was assessed by QUAST and MultiQC (Bankevich et al., 2012; Gurevich et al., 2013; Ewels et al., 2016). Assemblies were filtered based on contig lengths (>500bp and >1000bp) using a python script to investigate the impact of small contigs on the plasmid prediction. For clarity, the three filters were designated “F0”, “F500” and “F1000” to indicate the size of the contigs removed. *De novo* assembled contigs were then aligned using BWA with standard parameters against the respective reference chromosomes and plasmids to classify them as plasmid- or chromosome-related. Contigs that did not align on any sequence were considered as “chimeric” contig. These “truth” contigs were then used to assess the performance of the different plasmid tools.

2.2 Databases

PlaScope and MOB-recon predict plasmid contigs by using a database of known complete plasmids while HyAsP identify plasmid sequences by using known plasmid genes. In contrast to the other tools which use taxon-independent plasmid database, PlaScope was originally designed to target *particular species* so the default databases contains only plasmids from *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella*.

In this study, we have created three different plasmid databases to specifically target *S. enterica* plasmids and to examine the impact of the database content (taxon-independent vs targeted-species database) on the

performance of the plasmid prediction tools. The first database, designated “ALL+SE” was composed of 22494 plasmids and was created by merging all the complete plasmid sequences from PLSDDB (Galata et al., 2019) (downloaded on June 29th 2020) and COMPASS databases (Douarre et al., 2020), keeping only unique sequences by removing identical sequences using the clustering tool cd-hit-est (Li and Godzik, 2006). This database encloses 21414 plasmids sequences from 2335 species and 1080 sequences belong to *S. enterica*. The accession and the taxonomy of this plasmid database are listed in Supplementary Table S3. Two variants of this database were created by either keeping (“SE”; n=1080) or excluding (“ALL-SE” n= 21414) the plasmids recovered from *S. enterica*.

For MOB-recon, the plasmids of these three databases were first characterized by MOB-typer and clustered using MOB-cluster, two other modules from MOB-suite tool (Robertson and Nash, 2018). MASH distances between plasmid were also estimated using MASH (Ondov et al., 2016).

For HyASP, three gene databases were built through the create command of HyASP using an accession containing the different combination of plasmids mentioned above. Duplicate genes were removed from the collection with the argument (--dereplicate) and final number of plasmid genes in the database were 1174117, 1174117 and 24567 for the “ALL+SE”; “ALL-SE” and “SE” databases respectively.

A database containing 1107 complete chromosome sequences of *S. enterica* downloaded from the NCBI nucleotide archive on July 23th 2020 was also created. This database was used by PlaScope for chromosomal depletion. For all the databases created for this study, sequences from the 55 chromosomes and 81 plasmids of the reference dataset were excluded for evaluation purposes.

2.3 Plasmid Predictions

The 55 assembled genomes from the reference dataset were tested against the five selected prediction tools PlaScope, PlasFlow, HyASP, MOB-recon and Platon with different databases and filters that are summarized in the Table 1. All the tools were tested against the raw and filtered assemblies (F500 and F1000), except HyASP that perform plasmid prediction from graph files. By default, MOB-recon and Platon filtered all contigs smaller than 1kbp while PlaScope keep contigs bigger than 500bp. The script of these programs was therefore modified to test both contig length filters.

The three reference-based prediction tools PlaScope (1.3.1), HyASP and MOB-recon (3.0.0) were run with default parameters and specifying one of the three *in house* databases detailed above (Table1). PlasFlow (1.1) was carried out with a 0.7 probability threshold (default) and Platon (1.5.0) was run using three filter modes using different RDS discrimination thresholds: the “sensitivity mode” (RDS value below 7.9; used to exclude chromosomal contigs) the “specificity” mode (RDS value above 0.7) and the default “accuracy” mode which RDS value is below the sensitivity threshold and above the specificity threshold.

All the contigs predicted as plasmids were aligned against the “truth” plasmid contigs with blast+ and finally labelled either as chromosome, plasmid and chimer according to the single best blast+ hit. For the hybrid assembler HyASP, the sequences predicted as “putative_plasmid_contigs” were produced from the assembly graph (gfa) files and do not correspond to the assembly contigs. For the sake of comparability, another blast step was performed to align “HyASP contigs” to the original assemblies. Platon, MOB_recon and HyASP are binary classifier (“Plasmid” or “Chromosome” & “Putative” or “questionable”) while PlaScope and PlasFlow allow a third classification label “unclassified”. For comparative purposes, sequences assigned as “unclassified” were considered as chromosome-related and only putative plasmid contigs were further evaluated. The prediction performance of each individual tool tool using different parameters was first assessed before comparing the programs together.

Prediction Tool	Approach	Database type	DB (N° plasmid / Species)	Filters	Additional analysis	References
PlaScope	Reference-based	Plasmid	ALL+SE (22494 / 2336) ALL-SE (21414 / 2335) SE (1080 / <i>S. enterica</i>)	Contigs length (500 and 1000bp)	NA	Royer et al., 2018
MOB-suite	Reference-based	Plasmid	ALL+SE (22494 / 2336) ALL-SE (21414 / 2335) SE (1080 / <i>S. enterica</i>)	Contigs length (500 and 1000bp)	Reconstruction Characterization (REP & MOB typing) Identification	Robertson and Nash, 2018
PlasFlow	Machine learning (k-mer frequencies classification)	NA	NA	Contigs length (500 and 1000bp)	NA	Arredondo-Alonso et al., 2018
HyAsP	Reference-based & greedy assembly algorithm	Gene	ALL+SE (22494 / 2336) ALL-SE (21414 / 2335) SE (1080 / <i>S. enterica</i>)	NA	Reconstruction	Muller and Chauve, 2019
Platon	Protein-coding genes' replicon distributions	NA	NA	Contigs length (500 and 1000bp) Specificity / Accuracy / Sensitivity	NA	Schwengers et al., 2020

Table 1: Plasmid prediction tools, databases and filters used in this study

2.4 Performance of the prediction tools

The performance of the plasmid prediction tools were evaluated by calculating various scores (recall, precision, specificity, accuracy and F1 score) based on the presence of true/false positive/negative contigs (Royer et al., 2018; Muller and Chauve, 2019). True and false positives correspond to plasmid assignment of a plasmidic sequence (TP) or a non-plasmidic sequence (FP) while true and false negative correspond to chromosome or chimeric assignment of a non-plasmidic sequence (TN) and a plasmidic sequence (FN). Scores were then calculated as follows: recall (TP / (TP + FN)), precision (TP / (TP + FP)), specificity (TN / (FP + TN)), accuracy ((TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)) and F1 score (2 x (recall x precision) / (recall + precision)). TP and FN could not be determined for the five control samples because of the absence of plasmid sequences. Thus, the scores could not be calculated.

2.5 Plasmid characterization

Identifying plasmid-borne contigs from draft assembly is a critical step to analyze the plasmidome of microbial genomes. However, several bacterial species including *S. enterica* and other relevant *Enterobacteria* carry multiple plasmids. It is therefore important to reconstruct plasmids by identifying which contigs are associated with a particular plasmid. Among the bioinformatic tools tested, MOB-recon and HyAsP can reconstruct individual plasmid sequences from the predicted contigs. MOB-recon also identifies which cluster the new plasmids belongs to and determine the closest plasmid neighbour from the mash distance. Some plasmids can transfer between different bacterial species and replicate in a broad host range. The classification of plasmids based on replicon and MOB-typing is therefore very useful to examine the diversity and the transmission of Plasmids. MOB-recon can use another MOB-suite module, MOB-typer that will characterize core genes involved in the replication and the mobilization and provide full typing information such including Incompatibility group and putative mobility. In comparison to MOB-recon, Platon used the identification of several markers to predict plasmid-related contigs but do not characterize plasmids as such as MOB-recon.

Due to the clinical implications associated to resistance and virulence, it is also crucial to detect and annotate specific markers contributing to resistance and virulent phenotype. Several programs based on BLAST used specific databases to mine genes of interest. In this study, all the plasmids were screened for antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes using ABRicate (<https://github.com/tseemann/abricate>) with Resfinder and VFDB databases respectively.

Finally, we propose a pipeline combining bioinformatic tools for the entire exploration and annotation of the plasmidome of *S. enterica* from short reads data (Figure 1). The workflow involves the genome assembly performed by SPAdes, the identification of plasmid-borne contigs using PlaScope, the reconstruction and classification of plasmid sequences through MOB-recon/MOB-typer as well as the annotation of AMR determinants and virulence factors using ABRicate. This *in house* pipeline was applied to all the genomes of the test dataset.

Figure 1: In house pipeline for the identification, reconstruction and characterization of the *S. enterica* plasmidome

2.6 Test Dataset – *S. enterica* plasmidome

The plasmidome of a collection of 2863 *S. enterica* genomes was characterized using the pipeline described above. These genomes belong to 53 different serovars that were determined by *in silico* serotyping methods using SISTR (Yoshida et al., 2016). Among them, four serovars (Typhimurium and monophasic variant, Dublin and Derby) account for over 75% of all genomes present in the collection (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Serovar distribution of the test dataset composed of 2863 *S. enterica* isolates

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Reference dataset

The short reads of the 50 samples carrying plasmids were aligned against their corresponding reference sequences to make sure that reads cover the chromosome and plasmid sequences. The breadth of coverage was higher than 95% for 50 chromosomes and 79 plasmids belonging to 49 samples (Supplementary Table S4). In

contrast, the depth of coverage vary greatly between the 81 plasmids (from 5X to 5567X) and huge differences (> 20 fold) between chromosome and plasmid depth were observed for eight plasmids belonging to six samples (SAMN06045011, SAMN06045058, SAMN06045069, SAMN06045172, SAMN09237639 and SAMN09237640) (Figure 3). The number of these plasmid reads may result from their small sizes (< 6Kb) and their presence in multiple copies.

In total, 12189 contigs were assembled by SPAdes from the 55 genomes. The number of contigs varied from 75 (SAMN06030081) to 3092 (SAMN05172400) contigs with a median at 138 contigs. The MultiQC report obtained from QAST analyses is available in Supplementary Table S5. We intentionally leave the assembly from the sample SAMN05172400 that was fragmented and had a poor quality (NC50 = 5095) to see if the plasmid prediction was affected. The contig size distribution of the draft assemblies showed that on average, 58% and 70% of the contigs were smaller than 500 and 1000bp respectively (Figure 3). Accordingly, 6865 contigs were excluded when filtering the contig smaller than 500 bp while 8669 contigs were removed when keeping contig bigger than 1000bp.

Figure 3: Breadth coverage of the reference genomes and contig sizes distribution of draft assemblies

All the contigs were then aligned against their corresponding chromosome and plasmid sequences in order to classify them as “true” chromosomal-, plasmidic- or chimeric-borne contig. BLAST analysis showed that 404 contigs belonging to 78 plasmids were categorized as “true” plasmid sequences. Three small plasmids (CP030200.1, CP030201.1 and CP030199.1) belonging to SAMN06045068 were not covered by any of the assembled contigs and were therefore removed from the performance evaluation of the predicted tools. Among the 78 classified plasmids, 40 were only composed of a single contig while the other 38 were assembled from 2 to 50 contigs. In contrast, the number of “chimeric” contigs was much higher (n=2555) and varied considerably within genomes (from 4 to 404 contigs) and can represent up to 73% of the total contigs. However 94% of these chimeric associated-contigs were smaller than 1000 bp, thus accounting for maximum 4.45% of the total contig length (Supplementary Table S6). All the contigs from the control sample assemblies were classified as true chromosome contigs.

3.2 Plasmid Prediction Performance

Five recent *in silico* plasmid predictions tools were assessed by calculating different performance indicators based on the presence of True and False Positives. The three different plasmid databases created for this study were evaluated for PlaScope, MOB-recon and HyAsP whereas the filters on the contig length (F500 & F1000) were assessed for all the tools except HyAsP (Table 1).

PlaScope detected 225, 193 and 209 putative plasmid contigs for the three databases “ALL+SE”, “ALL-SE” and “SE” respectively. PlaScope reached the highest recall (0.64), precision (0.87) and F1 score (0.66) with the database “ALL-SE”. The values of these three indicators were slightly reduced for the other two databases containing *S. enterica* plasmids (Table). The specificity and the accuracy achieved by PlaScope obtained by the three databases were identical (0.97 and 0.99 respectively). The precision was the score varying the most (0.78 to 0.87) between the three databases with the lowest precision attained with the “SE” database. For the three databases, filtering small contigs (F500 and F1000) improved the Precision, while it didn't really affect the other metrics. No plasmid contigs were predicted for the CTL samples. Two plasmids were not detected at all by any of the three databases tested by PlaScope. The ALL-SE database which provide the highest overall performance failed to identify 5 plasmids of the 78 reference plasmids.

In comparison to PlaScope, **MOB-recon** predicted a very high number of plasmid contigs when using ALL+SE (3573) and SE (3489) databases. MOB-recon achieved the highest precision (0.69), specificity (0.99), accuracy (0.97) and F1 score (0.57) when using the ALL-SE database while the highest Recall (0.82) was attained by the ALL+SE database. In contrast to PlaScope, filtering small contigs improved all the indicators except the recall that obtained the highest value for the raw assembly (Supplementary table S7). The specificity and the accuracy obtained with the ALL+SE and SE databases were satisfactory (0.94 and 0.92 respectively). However the precision attained with these two databases was very poor (0.20 and 0.19) thus indicating that the presence of *S. enterica* plasmids sequences are responsible for the drop of precision. Indeed we observed ten times more FP were detected with the later databases in comparison with the ALL-SE database. The supplementary figure S1 also highlight that this precise database also have in return the lowest recall (0.53) as it failed to detect 17 plasmids. Overall, seven plasmids detected using MOB-recon by any of the databases. Similar results were observed for the control samples, the precise ALL-SE database produced less FP than the other.

HyAsP was the only prediction tool tested here that use the graph assembly file as input so the filters applied on the contig length could not be assessed with this program and only the results obtained from the three different gene databases were evaluated.

Similarly to MOB-recon, the number of predicted contigs was much higher for the two databases containing *S. enterica* plasmids than the ALL-SE database. The highest precision (0.78), specificity (0.99), accuracy (0.99) and F1 score (missing) was achieved with the “ALL-SE” database whereas the highest recall was obtained with the ALL+SE database (Figure 4). The accuracy and specificity obtained with the other two databases were also high (between 0.89 and 0.9 and 0.91) but their precision was very low (0.17 and 0.18) in comparison to the one attained by the “ALL-SE” database. Indeed, the total number of false positives produced by these two databases for all 50 samples is was twenty one times higher than the number of FP produced by the “ALL-SE” database. This findings indicate that the presence of some *S. enterica* plasmid sequences (among the 1080 sequences including in the databases) caused the decline of the precision. Overall 11 plasmids were not detected by any of three databases used by HyAsP. Figure 4 also showed that the database producing the most precise and accurate prediction attained the lowest recall (0.63) as it failed to detect 15 plasmids. Similarly to the samples, the analysis of the 5 control samples showed that the total number of False Positive was very high for the “ALL+SE” (FP=122) and “SE” (FP=112) database while the use of the “ALL-SE” database only produced 20 FP for two samples.

Figure 4: Performance of HyAsP using three plasmid databases created for this study (ALL+SE, ALL-SE & SE)

Platon was performed against the raw and filtered assemblies using three different modes “Accuracy” “Specificity” and “Sensitivity”. The highest recall score was obtained for the raw assembly with the sensitivity mode (0.94) followed by the accuracy (0.66) and the specificity mode (0.61). Platon achieves the highest precision (0.83), specificity (0.99) and accuracy (0.96) with the specificity mode whereas the best F1 score was attained with the accuracy mode (0.65). On the other hand, the specificity mode had the lowest recall (0.59) as it failed to identify 270 True plasmid contigs (Figure 5).

For all the different modes, filtering the contigs based on length decrease the number of False Positive but increase the number of False Negative thus reducing the recall and improving the other scores. However the Supplementary Figure S2 showed that the sensitivity mode is more affected by the filtering than the other two modes. Similar results were found for the five control samples, the specificity mode didn't detect any chromosomal-associated contigs and only one False Positive was predicted when using the accuracy mode. In contrast, the sensitivity mode produced 373, 30 and 11 FP for the raw and filtered assemblies. Three plasmids (CP039495.1, CP030228.1, and CP029998.1) were not detected at all by any of the three modes used while the accuracy and specificity modes failed to detect 4 and 8 plasmids in total, respectively.

Figure 5: Performance of Platon using three different filtering modes (accuracy, sensitivity and specificity)

PlasFlow is a prediction tool that do not use a reference database but employs a neural network approach for the identification of plasmid contigs. Consequently, only raw and filtered assemblies were tested and compared. PlasFlow predicted a huge number of plasmid contigs for the raw (4877) and filter assemblies (1655 and 800). Consequently, a considerable number of FP were detected even after excluding contig smaller than 1000bp (, thus causing a severe drop of the precision (0.46). In return, the number of FN identified was low and the recall values were between 0.7 to 0.86. The highest precision (0.46), specificity (0.96) accuracy (0.94) and F1 score (0.49) is attained when contigs smaller than 1000 bp were filtered while the best recall score (0.86) is obtained with the raw assemblies. Filtering contigs improved all scores except the recall by detecting less FP but missing in return true plasmid contigs (Figure 6). However, PlasFlow was able to detect at least one contig per plasmid. Chromosomal-related contigs were identified by PlasFlow in all the control samples of the three assemblies. As observed for the samples the total number of FP in the controls severely decreased when filtering contigs based on length.

Figure 6: Performance of PlasFlow using filters based on contig length (0bp, 500bp, 1000bp)

Our findings showed that the overall performance of HyAsP and MOB-recon varied depending on the database used and is balanced between specificity and sensitivity. Surprisingly, the database giving the best performance for these prediction tools was the one excluding *S. enterica* plasmids. The authors that developed HyAsP showed that the presence of three plasmid sequences from *S. enterica* that presented unusually chromosome-like characteristics was responsible for a severe drop in precision on *S. enterica* samples (Muller and Chauve, 2019). Two of these *S. enterica* plasmids (LN868945.1 and LN868946.1) were indeed present in the “SE” database and might have been the cause of the poor precision. These two sequences were removed and all the samples were tested again with this new database. However, the precision, even though slightly improved was still very low in comparison to the precision of the “ALL-SE” database indicating that other plasmid from *S. enterica* having chromosomal features might be also present. In comparison to MOB-recon and HyAsP, the performance of PlaScope was very similar between the three different databases although a slightly higher precision (0.87) was observed when using the ALL-SE database (0.83 and 0.85 for SE and ALL+SE). The accuracy and specificity modes of Platon produced similar results characterized by a high specificity (precision and accuracy) but a poor sensitivity (recall) while the sensitivity mode achieve opposite results. Filtering contigs based on length (F500 and F1000)

globally improved all scores beside the recall. However, MOB-recon, HyASP and PlasFlow were more impacted than the other predictions tools.

	Databases and Filters	recall	precision	specificity	accuracy	F1score
PlaScope	ALL-SE (F1000)	0,6180	0,8707	0,9981	0,9704	0,6559
MOB-recon	ALL-SE (F1000)	0,5314	0,6896	0,9949	0,9696	0,5658
HyASP	ALL-SE	0,6266	0,7861	0,9956	0,9775	0,6598
Platon	Specificity mode -F1000	0,5948	0,8385	0,9945	0,9692	0,6484
PlasFlow	F1000	0,7001	0,4635	0,9572	0,9380	0,4890

Table 2: Comparison of best plasmid prediction tool performance

The comparison of the different optimized prediction tools showed that all the tools reached high specificity and accuracy although PlasFlow reached lower scores than the other tools (Table 2). The precision is the indicator that varied the most (from 0.46 to 0.87 for PlasFlow and PlaScope) followed by the recall and F1 score. Plascope outperformed all the the other tools in precision and also attained highest F1 score along with HyASP and Platon. PlaFlow attained the highest recall (0.70) and the lowest precision (0.46) highlighting the balance between specificity and sensitivity.

Considering that F1 Score is the weighted average of Precision and Recal and that Accuracy and Specificity indicators produced very similar results, we summarized the global performance in the Figure 7 by plotting the specificity and F1 score metrics. This figure shows that the performance indicator scores tools varied across the collection of reference samples and the prediction tools and that PlaScope globally perfomed better than the other tools.

Figure 7: Performance summary (Specificity and F1 score) of the prediction tools with optimized parameters

3.3 *S. enterica* plasmidome

The *S. enterica* genome collection (n=2863) was tested with our new pipeline for the complete identification and characterization of the plasmidome. In total, 4626 contigs were identified by PlaScope in 1957 genomes and the number of plasmid contigs per genome vary from a single contig detected in 1044 genomes to 28 contigs in the genome 05CEB8920SAL (serovar Infantis). MOB-recon successfully reconstructed from these contigs 1894 plasmids which belong to 1124 genomes from 33 different serovar. The majority of *S. enterica* genomes (58%) carry a single plasmid while others can harbour up to eight plasmids (2004LSAL00112).

The vast majority (98.5%) of the plasmid neighbours identified using Mash distance from MOB-recon belong to 38 species of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family and were mostly represented by *E. coli* (56%) and *K. pneumoniae* (15%). This findings confirm previous studies showing that the transfer of plasmids among Enterobacteria species is frequent (Rozwandowicz et al., 2018). Another 28 plasmids were related to plasmids recovered from seven species including *Campylobacter coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Vibrio cholerae*.

Among the 1874 reconstructed plasmids, 1761 plasmids were categorized into 134 clusters from two to 131 plasmids (Cluster #AA798). Some of these clusters (#AA798, #AA800 and #AB039) contain plasmid that were restricted to a specific serovar (Derby, Agona and Typhimurium) whereas other groups (Clusters #AA014 and Clusters #AA349) contain plasmids that were distributed in different serovars thus indicating their transferability between unrelated strains.

All the plasmids were then screened for the presence of antimicrobial determinants. In total 680 resistance genes including 66 different variants were detected in 225 plasmids from 17 serovars (Figure 8). Genes conferring resistance to Aminoglycosides were the most frequent followed by Sulphonamides and Tetracyclines. The number of AMR markers per plasmid vary from one to 20 resistance genes encoded by the plasmid (#AA298) reconstructed from 201100992 assembly. Among all resistant plasmids, 52% were multiresistant (resistant to at least 3 different classes of antibiotics). The analysis of the plasmid types, their transferability and their AMR profile revealed interesting clusters that were either restricted to a specific serovar or distributed among unrelated *S. enterica* genomes:

- A large conjugative plasmid (Cluster #AA014) encoding *ant(3'')-Ia*, *sul1* and *tet(A)* genes that was recovered from 19 *S. enterica* infantis isolates.
 - A large IncC conjugative plasmid belonging to cluster #AA298 carrying from 18 to 20 resistance genes tha was detected in five Derby genomes
 - A small CoE10 mobilizable plasmid belonging to the cluster #AC745 and encoding *tet(C)* gene was reconstructed from 13 genomes belonging to serovars Bredeney, Typhimurium and Derby serovars.
 - A small mobilizable plasmid resistant to quinolone (*qnrB19* gene) and belonging to the cluster AA164 was detected in 10 strains from serovars Monophasic variant Typhimurium, Goldcoast, Schwarzengrund, Infantis & Muenchen
 - Two multiresistant plasmids (#AA176 and #AA036) reconstructed from 14 Monophasic variant Typhimurium
- Figure 8.

Figure 8: Distribution of AMR determinants among 225 reconstructed plasmids

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